

A Note on the Magnetic Susceptibility of certain Complex Molybdenum Compounds.

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In a previous paper to this journal (Rây and Bhar, 1928, 5, 497) it was shown that two of the complex molybdenum compounds examined behaved like the corresponding chromium complexes regarding their magnetic properties. The compounds studied were $K_2MoCl_6 \cdot 2H_2O$ and $(NH_4)_3Mo(SCN)_6 \cdot 4H_2O$. Both were found to obey Bose's rule giving a Bohr-magneton value of three each. This is evident from the effective atomic-numbers for the central molybdenum atom in them. The number in these cases is equal to $(42 - 3 + 12) = 51$, three units less than the atomic number for the nearest inert gas xenon (54). The valency of the molybdenum atom in these two compounds is three, corresponding to that of chromium in chromic complexes. On the other hand it was also found that (*loc. cit.*) the compound $K_4Mo(CN)_8 \cdot 2H_2O$ in which the molybdenum atom is tetravalent obeys Bose's rule as well, being diamagnetic, as the effective atomic-number of the central molybdenum atom in this case is equal to $(42 - 4 + 16) = 54$, the atomic number of xenon.

It is therefore of considerable interest to examine magneto-chemically other complex molybdenum compounds with a central molybdenum atom of a different valency. Complex co-ordination compounds of pentavalent molybdenum are known but as it is not easy to obtain them in a magnetically pure form, the study of these compounds was postponed till recently when through the courtesy of Dr. William Wardlaw of Birmingham, I was in possession of a number of these compounds of a degree of purity required for magnetic measurements.

The molecular formulæ of these compounds and the results of their susceptibility measurements are given in the following table.

TABLE I.

Compound.	$\chi_m \cdot 10^6$ at 29°	η_{Weiss}	η_{Bohr} (nearest),
1. $(C_5H_5N)_2MoOCl_5$. Dipyridinium molybdenyl pentachloride.	2.485	8.098	1
2. $(C_5H_5N)MoOBr_4$. Pyridinium molybdenyl tetrabromide.	2.157	8.128	1
3. $(C_5H_5N)_2MoOBr_4$. Dipyridinium molybdenyl pentabromide.	1.550	7.898	1
4. $(C_8H_7N)_2MoOBr_4$. Diquinolinium molybdenyl pentabromide.	1.140	7.257	1
5. $(C_8H_7N)MoOBr_4$. Quinolinium molybdenyl tetrabromide.	1.082	7.96	1

χ_m = mass susceptibility, η_{Weiss} = magneton number, η_{Bohr} = Bohr magneton number.

The physico-chemical properties of these compounds have been studied by James and Wardlaw (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 131, 2145). The compounds are much less stable than the trivalent molybdenum complexes. James and Wardlaw attribute their instability to the smaller effective atomic-number of the central molybdenum atom, the number being equal to 49 in these cases—5 units less than that for xenon. The magnetic susceptibilities however at first sight appear to be anomalous being much less than even that for trivalent molybdenum complexes.

There are two ways by which this anomaly can be explained.

In the first place if we assume these pentavalent molybdenum complexes as "perfect" co-ordination complexes, we can attribute to them the following electronic constitution.

TABLE II.

Effective atom No.	Substance.	Number of electrons in different levels.						
		K to M	N ₁₁ to N ₂₂	N ₃₂	N ₃₃	O ₁₁	<u>O₂₁ O₂₂</u>	
42	Mo atom	28	8	4		2		
49	Mo Complex	..	..	1	6		6	
47	Mo Covalent simple	..	..	1	6	2	2	

The six electrons of N_3 , being coupled with the six of O_2 , form the co-ordination bonds. The one lone electron in N_3 therefore is alone responsible for the paramagnetic susceptibility of the complex, as all the other levels are fully possessed.

Secondly one may view that these complexes are of an imperfect type resembling the double salts ; so that they may be regarded as double compounds of RCl and $MoOCl_3$ held by weak electrostatic attraction. The compound $MoOCl_3$ may reasonably be assumed to possess a co-valent structure whose electronic constitution may be represented as shown in the above table, where N_3 group remains incomplete having only one electron as before. The two structures thus resemble each other closely so far as the filling up of different levels are concerned. The magnetic susceptibility of $MoCl_5$, of which $MoCl_3$ is a derivative and which evidently possesses a co-valent structure, is approximately equal to one Bohr-magneton (Bose and Mukherjee—private communication). This seems to lend a strong support to this latter view. Which of the two views is more likely to represent the true constitution is difficult to decide at present without a röntgenographic study of the crystals which would throw light on the actual distribution of atoms and groups in the molecule.

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